

Question 1 – Usefulness

How can this project be interesting and useful from my point of view? How can it help me in my daily business:

Name:

Question 2 – Contribute with

How can I and my business/company contribute to that we move in the right direction. What can I do?

Name:

Question 3 – What is needed

What is needed if I should be able to fill my role in the project?

Name: